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STIMULATING REFLECTIVE SKILLS AMONG ENGINEERING (AND SCIENCE) STUDENTS – A CASE OF VISION, CURRICULUM, GUIDANCE AND TEACHER PROFESSIONALIZATION

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The contemporary knowledge society of the 21st century requires students, among other things, to have the ability to critically react to fast knowledge developments and to think analytically and reflectively (Walma-Van der Molen & Kirschner, 2017). Research into the disappearance of technical employees from the technical labor market also shows that it is important to guide students in their professional identity development, in which reflection of students is crucial. All in all, reflection is seen by several authors as an important competence for higher education students.

Various studies show that educational programs and teachers experience difficulty with the effective use of reflection in education. In addition, engineering and science programs indicate that the linguistic form in which reflection often takes place does not always seem to suit the technical target group, or that engineering and science students have more difficulty experiencing the meaningfulness of reflection. Two preliminary studies have examined how technical higher professional education programs have currently shaped student reflection in their curriculum and how students and lecturers experience this (see f.e. Woudt-Mittendorff & Pullen, 2019). The studies show results in recommendations at four different levels: a) Vision and goal setting, b) Curriculum/Programme, c) Guidance of reflection activities, and d) Teacher skills.

In the project 'Strengthening reflection in technical higher education programs', eight technical higher professional education programs of two Dutch higher education institutes are working on the improvement of reflection in their programs. With a project team they work on achieving a better vision and goals with regard to reflection within the programs (a), to concretize it at the programme level (b). Investments are also being made to improve reflection activities for students (c) and they pay attention to teaching skills (d). During two school years, steps are taken through various meetings with the teacher teams to give substance to the four levels mentioned.

The workshop is open to teachers and students. They will experience activities that are also undertaken within the aforementioned study programs. The workshop will consist of two rounds. Participants will first focus on the vision/ goal setting and programme level, and in the second round on the guidance level and teacher skills. Participants will learn about reflection and the importance of developing a vision on the topic and why the curriculum level is crucial. The literature shows that there is often a lack of clarity about the goals of reflection or that these goals are barely made explicit (Van Beveren, et al., 2018). Reflection can be used for different purposes or different "objects". The 'object' of reflection can be more or less specific,

and it can also relate to various things, for example to reflection on yourself, reflection on a process, a product, or even wider on society or your environment and the ethical side (Grossman, 2008). This workshop will provide insight into this and the participants will make the translation into their own educational practice. What are meaningful reflection goals for beta students? Is it mainly about professional development or do we want and to help beta students to grow in their personal awareness? And what does that mean for the use of reflection within the curriculum in years 1 to 4?

During round two, participants will participate in reflective activities that will address a) important design criteria for guiding students during reflection activities and b) the skills that are required by teachers. Literature shows that reflection is only effective if an individual is not merely reflecting by himself, but also relies on another (critical) person who thinks along, asks questions, gives feedback and helps reflect (Gabelica, Van den Bossche, Segers & Gijsselaers, 2012 ; Van Seggelen-Damen, van Hezewijk, Helsdingen & Wopereis, 2017). This guidance on reflection is best achieved in a dialogue (Meijers & Mittendorff, 2017) and is therefore an important ingredient for a good learning environment for reflection. However, the results of the preliminary studies show that students in technical courses still often have to reflect individually and usually in the form of a reflection report. Students indicate that they do not find this mode of reflection useful, and would prefer to reflect in the form of a conversation (see f.e. Woudt-Mittendorff & Pullen, 2019). In addition to their needs to reflect in conversational form, students also indicate that they lack guidance while reflecting. Where teachers often give students an assignment to reflect, they usually do not train or instructive students how to reflect and do not guide them during reflection activities.

Teachers need more clarity with regard to the concept of reflection, but especially to acquire skills to properly guide and assess reflection. During this workshop, handles and/or tools will be provided to shape reflection discussions. Participants will leave with an analysis of their own educational practice, as teacher of student, and with recommendations for future improvement.

To perform both rounds as well as possible, we opt for a 80-minute workshop.

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